

Mutual Recognition of Return Decisions: Quick Fix or Structural Challenge?

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Introduction

On 1 June 2026, the European Parliament and Council reached an agreement on the Regulation establishing a new Common European System for Returns (Legislative Proposal 2025/0059(COD)).

The reform is intended to address what is widely perceived as one of the most persistent weaknesses of EU migration policy: the limited effectiveness of return policy. Return procedures remain fragmented, unevenly implemented, and difficult to measure. In the period 2020–2024, only between 16% and 24% of non-EU nationals issued with an order to leave effectively returned to a third country.¹

Against this background, the agreed reform places strong emphasis on stricter rules, such as an extension of the detention period, strengthened obligation of cooperation for non-EU nationals and search rights for their place of residence. It also seeks to bring about stronger convergence and effectiveness.

Mutual recognition of return decisions is therefore expected to reduce duplication and limit delays, as well as discourage unauthorised secondary movements.

One of its main innovations is the gradual introduction of mandatory mutual recognition of return decisions, supported by the European Return Order (ERO) to be integrated into the Schengen Information System (SIS).

The agreement foresees a phased implementation of the mechanism via a preparatory two-year period after entry into application of the Regulation, during which mutual recognition remains optional and will be assessed by the Commission with a view to making it mandatory.

The intended logic is clear: once a return decision has been issued in one member state, another member state should not restart the procedure, in case of onward irregular movements. Mutual recognition of return decisions is therefore expected to reduce duplication and limit delays, as well as discourage unauthorised secondary movements. Yet additional flexibility inserted in the legislative text, as well as derogations, reflect remaining concerns about the practical implications of mutual recognition, especially operational constraints and the risk of administrative burden.

This Brief argues that the implementation of mutual recognition will require stronger convergence of return and asylum frameworks between member states, as well as more effective and reliable information-sharing. It also highlights the importance of meaningful incentives for mutual recognition and guidance on obstacles to removal linked protection of vulnerabilities and fundamental rights.

While the reform raises a degree of uncertainty about the impact of mutual recognition, it also offers an opportunity to generate new operational evidence and identify bottlenecks. In its future evaluation, the Commission should be able to assess not only preparedness, but also

whether the reform is effectively reducing divergences and addressing the obstacles that have limited the use of mutual recognition.

Background: A fragmented return system and the limits of mutual recognition

Until the entry into application of the Return Regulation, which is expected to take place one year after its adoption, the EU return system will function based on the 2008 Return Directive (Directive 2008/115/EC). One of the aims of this Directive was to streamline the return of non-EU nationals through common and effective standards and procedures.² The current framework also includes specific instruments aimed at facilitating cooperation between member states.

One of these is the Directive on the mutual recognition of expulsion decisions (Directive 2001/40/EC). This Directive predates the Return Directive and aimed to prevent non-EU nationals subject to a return decision from evading expulsion by crossing into another member state, thereby forcing the second state to re-start the return process.³ The Directive did not establish a mandatory mechanism for this. The broader framework includes another instrument⁴ that provides for the financial compensation of the enforcing member state by the issuing member state. Both instruments will be repealed by the new Regulation.

Mutual recognition of return decisions is therefore not a new concept; it has existed for over two decades. Yet it has seldom been used in practice. Despite the introduction of a compensatory mechanism, legal and operational divergences between member states remained.

Different national practices across member states have led to fragmentation, uneven levels of return rates and reduced overall effectiveness of the return system, also impacting the use of mutual recognition.

While the Return Directive and its complementary framework introduced a degree of harmonisation, different national practices across member states have led to fragmentation, uneven levels of return rates and reduced overall effectiveness of the return system, also impacting the use of mutual recognition.⁵

The Return Directive sets out minimum requirements but does not fully harmonise the content of return decisions. Over time, administrative practices and court decisions have played a key role in defining procedural guarantees and the elements to be included in decisions, such as those regarding the assessment of non-refoulement, the consideration of family life, and the best interests of the child.

Variations across member states also persist in the way return decisions are issued and enforced. These differences affect the application of fundamental rights safeguards in return procedures, including how risks are assessed, the extent of individualised evaluation, and the availability and scope of remedies. While obligations such as the principle of non-refoulement, the assessment of individual vulnerabilities, or the protection of family life are clearly established under EU law, their implementation remains embedded in national administrative and judicial frameworks. The Court of Justice of the European Union (CJEU) caselaw aimed to bring greater clarity and has, in part, generated more convergent practices. Yet some cases also gave rise to new obligations that, occasionally, increased the complexity of procedures and the disparities between member states.

All these elements have direct implications for mutual recognition. Its very nature requires member states to rely on return decisions issued elsewhere without a full (re-)assessment of the content of such a decision. But different practices and legal contexts affect both the willingness of authorities to rely on such decisions and the legal certainty of their enforcement.⁶ The European Arrest Warrant, which is based on the principle of mutual recognition, has encountered similar challenges in its execution as a result of concerns about fundamental rights and the need for additional harmonisation measures.⁷

These divergences are further compounded by differences in national asylum systems. Despite efforts towards harmonisation, recognition rates for international protection still vary significantly across member states,⁸ reflecting differences in both national procedures and the interpretation of protection grounds.

This has direct implications for return decisions. Such a decision is not a standalone act; it is often closely linked to the outcome of an asylum procedure and reflects a range of legal and factual assessments, including the absence of protection requirements, the existence of removal obstacles, and compliance with fundamental rights obligations.

An applicant who may be considered in need of international protection or who is eligible for a national humanitarian status in one member state could receive a negative asylum decision and a return decision in another member state because of differences in national assessments.

Where national authorities are aware that similar cases may lead to different outcomes across EU, they may be more reluctant to enforce return decisions from others, particularly given the fundamental rights implications and the possibility of being challenged before the courts. This creates incentives to rely on their own procedures to avoid significant administrative and financial costs.

Over time, the European Commission has launched several initiatives to enhance convergence. This includes the appointment of the EU Return Coordinator to improve coordination between relevant actors and help address operational challenges that hamper the effectiveness of return procedures,⁹ as well as practical tools such as the Return Handbook.

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Complementary operational measures have also been introduced. Return alerts in the Schengen Information System (SIS) to improve information-sharing are a notable example. These alerts aim to help identify non-EU nationals who are subject to a return decision in another member state, supporting the recognition of such decisions by providing information such as biographical data, voluntary return period, issuance of an entry ban, or enforcement status of the decision.¹⁰

However the effectiveness of information-sharing depends on the systematic entry, updating and follow-up of data in the SIS by national authorities. In practice, access to relevant data by national authorities often requires additional steps and information exchanges.

Another broader challenge is the lack of a sufficiently robust evidence base. Existing EU-level data does not allow for comprehensive tracking of return procedures, making it difficult to assess outcomes and the nature of obstacles.¹¹ The available data on return procedures is often fragmented, incomplete or difficult to compare across member states. Information remains limited on the reasons why returns are not enforced, the situations where an individual cannot be removed or the lack of follow-up from authorities in third countries. No reliable statistics exist on the use of mutual recognition either.

These constraints help to explain why national authorities have been reluctant or unable to resort to mutual recognition of return decisions, instead of starting a new process. Where its use has been more systematic, this was limited to facilitating transit through neighbouring EU member states to allow the exit of non-EU nationals from the Schengen area. In virtually all other cases, member states prefer to issue new return decisions.

This shows that mutual recognition is attractive if member states trust the decision-making process elsewhere and can enforce return decisions issued by other national authorities without significant legal risks or excessive operational or financial costs. Recognition of return decisions should not, therefore, be understood in isolation.

While it could enhance efficiency and reduce duplication, a higher level of convergence and operational capacity remain pre-conditions for it to work.

State of play: Mandatory recognition in a system still in transition

The Return Regulation seeks to address the challenges that have limited the effectiveness of the EU return system and make mutual recognition the default option where relevant. (The final text is now available (May 22, [Regulation - EU - 2024/1349 - EN - EUR-Lex](#))). The Commission's proposal illustrates the perceived political and operational importance of mutual recognition, describing it as a way to "discourage absconding and disincentivise secondary movements"¹² and to support simplification, speed and coherence in the future EU return system.¹³

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One of the key operational measures introduced by the agreed Regulation is the establishment of the European Return Order (ERO) and its integration into the SIS. The ERO provides a common format and improves access to information to facilitate recognition. Its content will be defined through an implementing act to be adopted six months after the entry into force of the Regulation. Then, member states, the Commission and relevant agencies will be required to put in place the legal, technical and operational arrangements necessary to process EROs through the SIS.

Despite the potential relevance of this change, the agreed reform reflects a rather cautious approach, establishing a phased system for the mandatory recognition of return decisions. The timeline for application was one of the last outstanding issues during negotiations, reflecting differing views on the pace of implementation. While the ERO is expected to become fully operational upon application of the Regulation, mandatory mutual recognition remains linked to a Commission evaluation to be carried out two years after the application of the Regulation.

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In this evaluation, the Commission is expected to assess whether legal and technical arrangements are in place to proceed with the mandatory mechanism, the effectiveness of the mutual recognition following the Regulation application, and the burden on judicial and administrative systems. The Commission will also have to consider the result of relevant pilot projects in its assessment.

During its initial preparatory phase, mutual recognition will thus remain optional for member states. Further reflecting this cautious approach, the text provides for broad possibilities to derogate from the mechanism. These include situations where enforcement would be contrary to national public policy, where issuing a new return decision would lead to a faster procedure, and where the information in the ERO is incomplete. Derogations are also possible where an appeal is pending in the issuing member state and where the return would concern a different third country than the one mentioned in the ERO.

While additional flexibility ensured buy-in and could preserve legal certainty, the reform may not create sufficient incentives for member states to rely on mutual recognition. In that context, national authorities may choose to adopt another return decision, if that proves simpler, clearer or less risky.

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Taken together, these characteristics of the agreed reform show that member states remain prudent about the prospects of mutual recognition. It may only become the default option if there is broader convergence between state practices, as well as suitable incentives and operational support. These include procedural differences regarding fundamental rights assessments; eligibility for protection; the stay of those subject to a return decision who cannot be returned; and gaps in information-sharing. Moreover, the reform does not set financial compensation for enforcing decisions issued abroad. All these constraints affect the use of mutual recognition and are examined in more detail below.

First, the reform preserves national return decisions and does not aim to fully harmonise their content. Several elements, such as assessments concerning non-refoulement or the right to family life, will continue to depend on national procedures. Similarly, some member states have a minimalistic approach to what is included in the content of return decisions, while others provide much more detail, also with respect to the aforementioned assessment.¹⁴

Second, the introduction of the ERO may not address this situation if it is to be based on a minimum level of convergence rather than a fully harmonised set of elements. For some member states, this may not provide sufficient detail to ensure legal certainty.

Third, this also increases the chances of litigation. Access to remedies should be guaranteed in the member state issuing the decision. Yet, non-EU nationals may still raise claims related to non-refoulement before the authorities or courts of the enforcing member state, in particular where new elements arise. This creates asymmetries in the distribution of accountability between issuing and enforcing authorities and could also indirectly put the ERO and its underlying assessments under scrutiny.

This evaluation raises a practical question: what will the Commission evaluation actually measure?

Fourth, the systematic use of mutual recognition depends on the quality, completeness, and timely updating of data entered in the SIS, as well as on the capacity of administrations to coordinate and act upon this information in practice. The reform places the SIS at the centre of the mechanism and aims to introduce automation in the handling of the ERO. However, it does not guarantee that the information available will be sufficiently accurate or complete for enforcement purposes. In addition, the current system of return alerts has not been evaluated, making it difficult to assess to what extent existing shortcomings could affect the ERO as it will require more information than existing alerts.

As mutual recognition will remain optional during the initial two-year preparatory phase, there may not be sufficient experience to test the operational viability and benefits of mutual recognition.

Fifth, the transition to mandatory mutual recognition could be further complicated by the Commission's future evaluation of the preparation and effectiveness of the mechanism. This evaluation raises a practical question: what will the Commission evaluation actually measure?

As mutual recognition will remain optional during the initial two-year preparatory phase, there may not be sufficient experience to test the operational viability and benefits of mutual recognition. An evaluation of a system that is only partially implemented may not capture how that system could simplify procedures, reduce delays or increase returns. It may also fail to identify the key elements for incentivising member states to use that system.

Furthermore, given that existing EU-level data does not allow for comprehensive tracking of return procedures across their different stages (i.e. identification, documentation, readmission and removal), this could make it harder to assess their outcomes and identify where gaps or bottlenecks occur.¹⁵

More broadly, and as a sixth point of consideration, the mutual recognition of return decisions is being introduced in a migration and asylum framework that remains in transition. The New Pact on Migration and Asylum (hereafter “the Pact”), the comprehensive reform of the Common European Asylum System, entered into application on 12 June 2026¹⁶ with the aim of streamlining migration and asylum processes and addressing long-standing shortcomings of the EU asylum framework.¹⁷ As part of this effort, the Pact also seeks to strengthen the link between asylum and return procedures.¹⁸

Yet the Pact reforms will not lead to full convergence in the underlying assessments that precede return decisions. While it harmonises asylum rules to a greater extent than under the previous framework, the convergence of protection outcomes depends on a broader range of factors where harmonisation is not fully achieved. This includes procedural frameworks, administrative organisation and the application of national humanitarian status. Reflecting persistent differences in the protection outcomes, the Pact does not establish a system of mandatory mutual recognition of asylum decisions.

In addition, there is no harmonisation of legal stay conditions across member states, which means that non-EU nationals could be eligible for a legal stay in one member state and not in another.

As a result, significant differences in decision-making are likely to persist, at least in the short to medium term. Convergence will therefore likely remain a policy objective rather than an operational reality.

Financial considerations may also affect the willingness of member states to apply mutual recognition. While the Return Regulation recognises the need for legal, technical and operational arrangements, the new rules do not establish what funds will cover costs linked to the enforcement of return decisions issued by another member state. Among the possible options, the member state issuing the decision could provide for compensation or, alternatively, EU-funding could support the process.

It is also unclear if and how additional costs would be compensated in scenarios where the return decision cannot be enforced due to obstacles related to documentation, cooperation with third countries or non-refoulement concerns. Clarifying this outstanding point

and establishing a clear and transparent mechanism would be especially important for member states facing the prospect of having to recognise a significant number of return decisions.

Prospects: Building the conditions for effective mutual recognition

The Return Regulation aims to make the EU common return system more effective. Mutual recognition is seen an important element of this effort. However its effective use will depend on addressing remaining operational challenges as well as a broader convergence between asylum and return frameworks. Its effectiveness will also depend on the quality of information shared between national authorities, and the readiness and content of the European Return Order.

Attention should therefore not be limited to the formal introduction of mandatory mutual recognition, but also to the conditions under which it can be expected to function in practice. To support the effective use of mutual recognition, this Policy Brief recommends the following actions:

➔ Ensure that the ERO contains sufficient, qualitative, and updated information

Considering the significant differences between member states' return decisions, a lack of information pushes national authorities to opt for the more exhaustive assessments guaranteed by their national procedures. The Commission should avoid an overly minimalist approach and specify what information must be included and kept updated throughout the procedure. Beyond individuals' administrative data, the ERO should cover at a minimum the enforceability of the decision, the country of return, pending remedies and exhaustive fundamental rights and non-refoulement assessments. Without this information, member states would need to coordinate further and request additional information or reassess elements that may not have been examined in the issuing member state. This also requires identifying and addressing shortcomings in the information contained in SIS return alerts.

➔ Ensure that the SIS is operationally prepared to support mutual recognition

Learning from the practical functioning of the existing return alerts system is an essential preliminary step towards an effective system of mandatory mutual recognition. The introduction of return alerts is relatively recent and has not yet been comprehensively evaluated. The Commission should ensure that any future assessment goes beyond technical readiness and provides a comprehensive overview of the effectiveness of return alerts in practice, including the quality and completeness

of data recorded and the frequency of additional requests between member states. The Commission should also identify operational shortcomings and support the development of corrective measures.

➔ Provide guidance on how to address new elements after a return decision has already been issued, including vulnerabilities and other obstacles to removal

New elements could arise in the period between an issuing member state's return decision and its enforcement in another state. These could include changes in circumstances that may have an impact on enforcement and on the prospects for return. The Commission, in cooperation with relevant EU agencies, should clarify how enforcing authorities should deal with such situations involving new elements. This should include whether national authorities can partially or fully re-examine the decision or carry out further fundamental rights assessments. The EU Fundamental Rights Agency (FRA) could also be involved in the future process, providing guidance on the conditions for such assessments. This would reduce uncertainty while preventing the systematic issuing of new return decisions.

➔ Ground the implementation of mutual recognition in systematically collected evidence

The rollout of mutual recognition should be grounded in a more realistic assessment of the current level of convergence of asylum and migration policies across member states. Before accelerating towards mandatory mutual recognition, the Commission should ensure that the system is effectively tested on the basis of sufficient evidence generated during the first preparatory phase. The evaluation should be closely linked to actual use of EROs once these are fully operational, mapping if and when mutual recognition is actually used, and why. It also depends on accurate data across the return procedure, to better understand how decisions are followed up and where bottlenecks occur. The Commission should also assess whether Pact reforms are leading to closer alignment in national practices, as well as the impact and risks that any remaining divergence may have on mutual recognition.

➔ Support member states financially and operationally when they enforce return decisions issued elsewhere

The Commission and the Council should establish clear arrangements regarding the allocation of funds and compensation linked to the enforcement of return decisions issued by another member state. In the absence of compensation arrangements between concerned member states, co-legislators should ensure that the financial implications are adequately addressed in the next Multiannual Financial Framework, notably through the AMIF for the 2028-2034 period. It should also be clarified whether member states should benefit from additional

assistance if the process does not lead to an actual return. This would not only incentivise the use of mutual recognition, where appropriate. It would also enable national authorities to better plan the use of their resources when facing the prospect of higher administrative or operational workloads.

➔ Mobilise resources such as the EU Return Coordinator and Frontex to support the practical uptake of mutual recognition

Other than ensuring closer coordination between member states, the EU Return Coordinator could play a strong role in identifying practical obstacles to mutual recognition. During the initial preparatory phase when use of mutual recognition is optional, the Return Coordinator could also monitor when and how the mechanism is used, paving the way for a more reliable and comprehensive assessment by the Commission two years after the Regulation's entry into application. At the same time, Frontex's role in the operational follow-up of recognised return decisions, including return assistance and targeted support where implementation pressures are high, should also be assessed in the context of the new rules. More specifically, Frontex's involvement could ensure that capacity constraints do not become a disincentive to use mutual recognition. Finally, the EU Asylum Agency should have a role to play in ensuring convergence in protection outcomes and vulnerability assessments.

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